

Sea ice controls phytoplankton seasonality in the Southern Ocean

Supplementary Code and Software Readme file

Megan Lenss, Martin Vancoppenolle, Sébastien Moreau

This repository contains software and code used in the framework of the submitted paper “Sea ice controls phytoplankton seasonality in the Southern Ocean”, by Lenss et al. (Lenss, Moreau, Campbell, Naëck, Chierici, Vancoppenolle, submitted).

Contents of the online repository

- **L2**: scripts doing the figures presented in the paper.
- **Ice_float_years.mat** : Mat-file with pre-processed data (see description below)
- **sidays_OSI-SAF-450-430b_sh_2014_2022_clim.nc** : OSI-SAF climatology of sea ice season duration
- **FIGS**: PNG graphics files for each float-yr.
- **L1**: pre-processing scripts converting raw float data into interpretable float years.

The figures can be reproduced using L2_scripts, based on Ice_float_years.mat with pre-processed data. Only advanced users would want to use L1_scripts. To do so, they would need to download ERA5 data of atmospheric temperature, winds and shortwave radiation

(<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>), as well as OSI-SAF 450-430 sea ice concentration data (<https://osi-saf.eumetsat.int/products/osi-450>), for 2014-2022.

1. System requirements

All software dependencies and operating systems (including version numbers)
Versions the software has been tested on

L1 Software has been tested on Matlab 2018 & MacOS Sequoia 15.7.7 and on Windows 11 version 25H2 (OS Build 26200.8390) with Matlab version R2026a.

L2 Software has been tested on Windows 11 version 25H2 (OS Build 26200.8390) with Matlab version R2026a.

2. Installation guide

Typical install time on a "normal" desktop computer : a few minutes with Matlab installed.

Required toolboxes and packages:

- Matlab Mapping Toolbox
- Matlab Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox
- Antarctic Mapping Tools
- Antarctic boundaries, ground line, and masks from InSAR

Each script comes up with an input directory.

L1 scripts pre-process the float data. Directories should be adjusted to make sure input data can be accessed.

L2 scripts will produce all 8 figures included in the manuscript as well as calculate the integrated mixed-layer PAR and run the floats through the quasi-Lagrangian criteria.

3. Description of L2 scripts (data analysis)

calculate_lz.m: Calculates integrated mixed-layer PAR for each ice-year and saves it in the data matrix.

quasiLagrangianTest.m: This script runs all 108 ice-years through the three criteria to test for Lagrangian movement. It saves a mask to the data matrix for the 34 floats identified as quasi-Lagrangian called the platinumMask.

Figure1.m: This script produces the first figure in the manuscript, a map of the float trajectories over a sea-ice climatology during the 8 year deployment period.

Figure2.m: This script produces the second figure in the manuscript. First it calculates integrated losses in phytoplankton biomass (C_{phyto}) and then it calculates the three phenological indicators, r , μ , and ℓ . These three parameters are then plotted in sea-ice time.

Figure3.m: This script produces the third figure in the manuscript plotting six physical parameters in sea-ice time: mixed-layer median temperature, mixed-layer median salinity, sea-ice concentration, median integrated mixed-layer nitrate, mixed layer depth, and mixed-layer integrated PAR.

Figure4.m: This script produces the fourth figure in the manuscript plotting four biological parameters in sea-ice time: mixed-layer integrated chl a , mixed-layer integrated POC, mixed-layer integrated C_{phyto} , and mixed-layer integrated losses.

supplementaryFigure1.m: This script produces the first supplementary figure in the manuscript. First it calculates integrated losses in phytoplankton biomass (C_{phyto}) and then it calculates the three phenological indicators, r , μ , and ℓ . These three parameters are then over a normal time axis based on days of the year numbered 1-366.

supplementaryFigure2.m: This script produces the second supplementary figure in the manuscript. This is a sensitivity analysis of the PAR calculations and tests 3 different levels of PAR transmittance through the sea ice: 10%, 5% and 1% transmittance. These three tests are then plotted over sea-ice time as in Figure 3.

supplementaryFigure3.m: This script produces the third supplementary figure in the manuscript. This is a sensitivity analysis for the C_{phyto} : chl a ratio used in the analysis. Here

the phenological indicators r , μ , and l are calculated with two different ratios to demonstrate robustness.

supplementaryFigure4.m: This script produces the fourth supplementary figure in the manuscript. This is a sensitivity analysis for the chl *a*: nitrate ratio used in the analysis. Here, 10 different ratios are tested and ice-year 4 is plotted and shown as an example of this sensitivity analysis.

4. Description of L1 scripts (pre-processing)

float 1 vertical interpol.m

1. Read all float data
2. Interpolate on standard vertical grid (2000 1-m-separated depths)
3. Hard-coded data cleaning
4. Save [*Ice_floats.mat*](#)
5. Do contour plots for one selected individual file (optional).

float 2 colocate siconc.m

1. Colocate sea ice with float position
2. Overwrite [*Ice_floats.mat*](#)

float 3 colocate era5.m

1. Colocate ERA5 (tair, u-wind, v-wind)
2. Overwrite [*Ice_floats.mat*](#)

float 4 1D diags.m

1. Calculate mixed layer (using *v2* algorithm)
2. Calculate surface and subsurface diagnostics
3. Overwrite [*Ice_floats.mat*](#)
4. Contour plot for all files with Tair and SIC (optional)

float 5 split.m

1. Differentiate ice concentration (guess *ia* & *ir*)
2. Delimit float years (automatic & hard-coded)
3. Flag completeness of seasonal cycles
4. Create a float_yr index in float space
5. Unfold float data into float years
6. Float time axes
7. Count ice season and open ice duration
8. Count data for each variable (complete and incomplete years)
9. Count complete seasonal cycles, etc... (hard-coded with float_yr.status)
10. Save [*Ice_floats_years.mat*](#)

float 6 key dates.m

1. Identify key dates

Overwrite *ice_floats_years.mat*

5. Methodological details for pre-processing

Reshuffling float series onto ice-years

- 40 floats from the sea ice zone for the period 2014-2022 were extracted from the SOCCOM database
- We aimed to phase float hydrography with sea ice concentration. As float full-records encompass several years, we split them into individual ice-years.
- To this end, closest satellite SIC concentration (OSI-SAF) values were colocalized for each cast.
- In the seasonal ice zone, an ice-year is characterized by two periods: ice-covered and ice-free seasons. The first-day with ice is termed « date of advance », and last day with ice is termed « date of retreat », the difference between both being the ice season duration. Dates of advance and retreat were diagnosed for each float record. As float records encompass several years, each float full record can have several ice advance and retreat dates.
- Based on ice advance and retreat dates, each float was then split into individual ice-years, by a combination of an automated procedure, corrected by manual examination.
- Based on this, we end-up with float-cast series over four types of ice-years
 - series with not even a complete ice season (status = -1)
 - series with a complete ice season, but no or incomplete water season (status = 0)
 - series with complete ice and water seasons (status = 1)
 - series with complete sea ice and water seasons, plus a few records before ice advance (status = 2)
 - Multi-year ice was assumed to have status = 0.
- Hydrography records were then re-organized into individual ice-years.

Ice-year time axes

We redefined several time axes

- **doy** : day of the year goes from 1-365/6 for each year. Not useful as the open water season often goes beyond Dec 31, as ice advance is typically after Feb 15.
- **doy_expd** : expanded day of year is day-of-year, expanded into the following year so that it starts from 1 but goes beyond 365/6 for the last records.
- **doy_shft** : expanded day of year shifted to have advance as being day zero.
- **doy_sqzd** : shifted-and-squeezed time axis, so that advance is zero and retreat is one.
- **doy_sqzd2** : **shifted-and-squeezed time axis, with advance being zero, retreat being one, and next advance being two.**

Mixed layer calculation

Mixed layer calculation is based on a simple density threshold algorithm. Mixed layer depth is the depth at which density is larger than the surface value than the surface value by a threshold of 2 kg/m³.

All diagnostics are averaged over the mixed layer, and also over the sub-surface, defined as 200-500 m.

6. Contents of the Ice_floats_years.mat file

Variable	Dimension	Description	Comment
status:	[108×1 double]	Ice season status	-1: uncomplete ice season, 0: complete ice season / incomplete water season, 1: complete ice / water seasons, 2: complete ice/water seasons + extra time before beginning
N_fy:	108	Number of « float-years »	
N_casts_max:	55	Maximum number of casts per year	
N_casts:	[108×1 double]	Number of casts for each float year	
yr:	[108×55 double]	Year for each cast within each float-year	
lon:	[108×55 double]	Longitude, for each cast within each float-year	
lat:	[108×55 double]	Latitude, for each cast within each float-year	
decy:	[108×55 double]	Decimal year, for each cast within each float year	
doy:	[108×55 double]	Day-of-year, for each cast, within each float year	
mon:	[108×55 double]	Month, for each cast, within each float year	
dom:	[108×55 double]	Day in the month, for each cast, within each float year	
zml:	[108×55 double]	Calculated mixed layer depth, for each cast within each float year	
T_mld:	[108×55 double]	Mixed layer temperature, for each cast, within each float year	
S_mld:	[108×55 double]	Mixed layer salinity, for each cast, within each float year	
NO3_mld:	[108×55 double]	Mixed layer NO3, for each cast, within each float year	
Chla_mld:	[108×55 double]	Mixed layer Chla, for each cast, within each float year	
DIC_LIAR_mld:	[108×55 double]	Mixed layer DIC-LIAR for each cast, within each float year	
TA_LIAR_mld:	[108×55 double]	Mixed layer TA-LIAR for each cast, within each float year	

pCO2_LIAR_mld:	[108x55 double]	Mixed layer pCO2-LIAR for each cast, within each float year	
DIC_CANY_mld:	[108x55 double]	Mixed layer DIC-CANY for each cast, within each float year	
TA_CANY_mld:	[108x55 double]	Mixed layer TA-CANY for each cast, within each float year	
pCO2_CANY_mld:	[108x55 double]	Mixed layer pCO2-CANY for each cast, within each float year	
T_sub:	[108x55 double]	Sub-surface temperature	
S_sub:	[108x55 double]	Sub-surface salinity	
NO3_sub:	[108x55 double]	Sub-surface nitrate cc	
Chla_sub:	[108x55 double]	Sub-surface chla	
DIC_LIAR_sub:	[108x55 double]	Sub-surface DIC-LIAR	
TA_LIAR_sub:	[108x55 double]	Sub-surface TA-LIAR	
pCO2_LIAR_sub:	[108x55 double]	Sub-surface pCO2-LIAR	
DIC_CANY_sub:	[108x55 double]	Sub-surface DIC-CANY	
TA_CANY_sub:	[108x55 double]	Sub-surface TA-CANY	
pCO2_CANY_sub:	[108x55 double]	Sub-surface pCO2-CANY	
a_i_OSI:	[108x55 double]	Colocalized SIC from OSI-SAF, for each cast, within each float year	
t2m:	[108x55 double]	Colocalized ERA5 2m air temperature, for each cast, within each float year	
wspd:	[108x55 double]	Colocalized ERA5 Wind speed, for each cast, within each float year	
name:	[108x1 string]	Unique ID of each float year (floatID_year00_year)	
floatno:	[108x1 double]	Serial number of the source float (1-41)	
yearno:	[108x1 double]	Serial number of the year in the float record (1-5)	
doy_expd:	[108x55 double]	<i>Expanded</i> doy, for each cast, within each float year	
doy_shft:	[108x55 double]	<i>Shifted</i> time axis, for each cast, within each float year	
doy_sqzd:	[108x55 double]	<i>Squeezed</i> time axis, for each cast, within each float year	

doy_sqzd2:	[108x55 double]	<i>Squeezed</i> time axis (v2) for each cast, within each float year	
i_adv:	[108x1 double]	Cast number of ice advance, for each float year	
i_ret:	[108x1 double]	Cast number of ice retreat, for each float year	
da:	[108x1 double]	Sea ice advance date for each float year	
dr:	[108x1 double]	Sea ice retreat date for each float year	
isd:	[108x1 double]	Sea ice season duration for each float year	
T	[108x2001x55 double]	Vertically-resolved T hydrographic data	
S	[108x2001x55 double]	...	
Sig	[108x2001x55 double]		
Chla	[108x2001x55 double]		
POC	[108x2001x55 double]		
NO3	[108x2001x55 double]		
DIC_CANY	[108x2001x55 double]		
DIC_LIAR	[108x2001x55 double]		
TA_CANY	[108x2001x55 double]		
TA_LIAR	[108x2001x55 double]		
pCO2_CANY	[108x2001x55 double]		
pCO2_LIAR	[108x2001x55 double]		

7. Float metadata

Table 1. Float-year statistics, classified according to a seasonal cycle coverage score. For each score category, the number of float-years as well as the minimum, median and maximum number of casts over float years with the corresponding score are given

Score	N _{ice-years}	N _{casts}			Seasonal cycle status
		min	med	max	
-1	14	5	16.5	41	not a complete sea ice season
0	24	6	34	48	complete sea ice season but no or incomplete water season (incl. MY ice)
1	46	27	36	46	complete sea ice season
2	24	37	45.5	55	complete sea ice season + extra obs before advance

Table 2. Number of records for each variable (lines), according to seasonal cycle completeness score (see Table 1).

	All floats		-1		0		1		2	
	LIAR	CANY	LIAR	CANY	LIAR	CANY	LIAR	CANY	LIAR	CANY
lat	3752		248		771		1645		1088	
lon	3752		248		771		1645		1088	
date	3759		249		775		1645		1090	
SIC	3752		248		771		1645		1088	
S	3576		248		722		1535		1071	
T	3576		248		722		1535		1071	
MLD	3576		248		722		1535		1071	
DIC	1317	1317	130	130	269	269	450	450	468	468
TA	3539	3561	245	245	718	718	1513	1535	1063	1063
pCO ₂	1316	1315	130	130	269	268	450	450	467	467
Chla	3408		240		675		1534		959	
NO ₃	3410		230		638		1500		1042	

Table 3. Full list of available SOCCOM floats in the sea ice zone, with minimum latitude, longitude, year of deployment, number of complete years, number of retained records and thrown records.

Float name	lat _{min}	lat _{max}	lon _{min}	lon _{max}	y _{min}	y _{max}	N _{float-years}	N _{valid}	N _{thrown}
5904397	-63	-59	0	360	2015	2020	5	181	0
5904860	-73	-70	186	214	2017	2019	2	80	1
5905634	-71	-70	186	190	2018	2019	1	31	0
5905994	-66	-64	319	329	2019	2022	3	117	2
5906006	-61	-57	333	341	2019	2020	1	49	1
5904468	-67	-64	0	360	2015	2020	5	188	0
5905075	-71	-67	254	262	2017	2019	2	81	0
5905636	-71	-67	201	211	2018	2022	4	137	1
5905995	-68	-66	333	348	2019	2022	3	118	0
5906033	-67	-66	13	30	2019	2022	3	111	2
5904469	-63	-51	0	360	2014	2019	2	63	97
5905077	-68	-48	234	329	2017	2021	2	90	62
5905637	-73	-68	183	210	2018	2022	4	131	0
5905997	-65	-63	113	121	2019	2022	4	127	0
5906034	-65	-61	26	33	2019	2022	3	114	0
5904471	-69	-64	0	360	2014	2019	5	159	0
5905078	-67	-66	231	239	2017	2018	1	48	0
5905638	-70	-68	161	175	2018	2022	3	92	4
5905998	-65	-60	102	128	2018	2022	4	126	0
5906210	-65	-64	54	61	2020	2021	2	50	0
5904472	-70	-65	314	358	2015	2019	4	147	4
5905367	-65	-63	70	87	2017	2018	1	23	0
5905639	-69	-67	230	248	2018	2022	4	145	2
5906000	-64	-54	79	112	2018	2022	3	91	38
5906211	-63	-58	52	57	2020	2022	2	78	0
5904855	-69	-67	264	282	2017	2021	4	157	0
5905374	-65	-63	136	158	2018	2019	2	61	0
5905991	-64	-54	313	357	2019	2022	2	78	52
5906001	-64	-59	80	92	2018	2019	1	24	0
5906227	-69	-58	273	317	2020	2022	2	69	20
5904857	-76	-68	171	204	2017	2022	5	154	7
5905375	-65	-58	137	164	2018	2020	1	35	59
5905992	-67	-57	329	354	2019	2022	3	128	4
5906003	-60	-53	308	349	2019	2021	0	0	93

5906228	-70	-69	263	270	2020	2021	1	38	0
5904859	-71	-69	251	274	2017	2022	5	148	5
5905379	-66	-63	150	168	2018	2022	4	143	6
5905993	-74	-69	323	353	2019	2020	1	41	0
5906005	-60	-59	329	333	2019	2021	3	99	0
5906496	-67	-67	0	360	2022	2022	1	7	0